

MODERN APPROACHES IN TEACHING BIOLOGICAL SCIENCE.

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Abstract: In this thesis, it is briefly shown how to make students studying in the schools of the Ministry of Secondary Special Education of our country more interested in natural science and biology, and how to teach lessons in an easy and interesting way.

Key words: Biology, Methodology, System, Lesson, Stage, Conclusion

The main part: The world around us is full of mysteries. Why do animals act the way they do? Why do plants grow the way they do? Why do certain processes occur in our body? Man has been striving for knowledge of these things since time immemorial. He learns all this through the science of "Natural History". In our time, this science is called Biology.

In Greek, "bios" means life, "logos" means science. Biology is a science that studies living organisms, plants and their structure, characteristics, and living environment. Modern biological science not only collects information about various organisms, but also seeks to study their interrelationships and general characteristics. For example, this science seeks to study the relationship of man with millions of living creatures, how they affect human development. Biologists are determined to unravel the great mystery of how life first appeared on Earth and what form it took. In order to achieve this, they studied the various conditions necessary for life and created a classification and archive of all living organisms on our planet. In their research, scientists look for answers to all questions from nature itself, to find them they dive to the depths of the oceans, climb skyscrapers, high peaks, cross impassable thickets and swamps. They pass by and sit staring at the ring microscope. Therefore, they tirelessly search for the secrets of life, and even conduct strange researches for this.

Development of a scientific worldview in accordance with the current state of natural sciences in the course of teaching biology is of particular importance for high

school students who have increased interest in philosophical problems in connection with the natural need for a holistic perception of reality. School biology, unlike other subjects, helps to demonstrate the power of knowledge through a systematic and historical approach to natural phenomena. In the course of teaching biology, together with the development of dialectal thinking of schoolchildren, the scientific view of the organic world, the historicity of life and its place in the system of movement, are revealed in them with contrasting ways of knowing. Biology is one of the leading subjects of the science cycle in the school system, because it is of great importance in the formation and development of a person.

Conclusion: There are many modern approaches to teaching biology. These approaches help make the learning process interesting and interactive. For example, virtual laboratories, interactive tutorials, animations, and 3D models can be used. In addition, through online tests, quizzes and forums, students can test their knowledge and communicate with each other. These methods help students learn and understand biology and increase their scientific reasoning.

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